

FOCUS, improving detection of pinewood nematode infected trees through remote sensing methods

Vasco M. Mantas¹, Luís Fonseca², Isabel Abrantes², Christina Aas³, Nicolas Lewyckyj⁴

¹Department of Earth Sciences, University of Coimbra,, Portugal; ²CFE-Centre for Functional Ecology-Science for People & the Planet, Department of Life Sciences, University of Coimbra,, Portugal; ³Science & Technology, Norway; ⁴Vlaamse Instelling Voor Technologish Onderzoek N.V., Belgium.
vasco.mantas@dct.uc.pt

<http://focus.uc.pt>

Bursaphelenchus xylophilus management in European forests can be achieved if timely and accurate information on the distribution of infected trees is available. Remote sensing provides the most promising tool to accomplish near-real time detection of wilting trees. Insufficient information is currently available, hampering the operational deployment of monitoring services.

Project FOCUS (*Forest Operational Monitoring Using Copernicus and UAV data*) is funded by the European Union (H2020, Grant Agreement 776026) and brings together different players in Europe and the United States of America including academia, investigation/technology companies, and forest stakeholders.

Objectives

To detect healthy and wilting maritime pines

To develop algorithms using multi- and hyperspectral data

To engage stakeholder during product development & testing

To integrate data into the operational Silvisense service

